

D7.7 Policy Brief “Vision for excellence in marine and freshwater RIs”

Seascope Belgium

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Executive Summary

This document details the AQUARIUS project's vision of excellence in marine and freshwater RIs, proposing a post-project future that will maintain AQUARIUS' legacy and continue to support the Mission 'Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030'. Prepared at the mid-point of the AQUARIUS project, this vision will develop in the context of the evolving landscape of relevant European and international policy and initiatives.

The AQUARIUS Vision has been developed through a collaborative process engaging all partners in the AQUARIUS project. A questionnaire was circulated to all project partners during 2025, gathering ideas and opinions on the main value of AQUARIUS and the key components that are priorities to sustain after the project ends.

The AQUARIUS' strategic vision is for **a sustained European service to support marine and freshwater research infrastructures**, and the excellent science they facilitate, in support of the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030", implementation of the European Ocean Pact, and other European and international policy initiatives.

The sustained AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater research infrastructures includes:

- A resourced programme for **transnational access** to European marine and freshwater research infrastructures for research teams worldwide
- Technical **training** opportunities and resources for early career researchers and technicians, e.g. by maintenance of the AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub and Materials Repository
- **Data management** and Open Science support, e.g. by maintenance of the AQUARIUS Data Flow Dashboard and data pathways to EMODnet and the European Digital Twin Ocean.
- A living **inventory of European marine and freshwater research infrastructures**, including their technical and scientific capabilities and facilities, e.g. by maintenance, expansion and further development of the AQUARIUS catalogue
- Facilitation of a **forum for marine and freshwater RI operators and technicians** to share expertise, best practices and support.

Realisation of AQUARIUS' strategic vision for European Marine and Freshwater Research Infrastructures will be **critical to continue to support excellent, internationally collaborative aquatic science**, as demonstrated during the AQUARIUS project.

Beyond supporting excellent science and research, the envisioned AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater research infrastructures will support implementation of a range of ambitious policies, initiatives and strategic activities for Europe, including the **Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030"**, the **European Ocean Pact** and the **Ocean R&I Strategy**, EU and international **environmental policy**, the **All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA)**, the **European Research Area** and the **UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development**.

The record of the AQUARIUS project clearly demonstrates the demand for the services it offers, and the impactful research it facilitates. It also demonstrates the effectiveness of such a model for coordination of RIs. **Simply, AQUARIUS works.**

With limited resources and a complex existing landscape of European marine and freshwater entities, programmes and RIs, implementation of a sustained AQUARIUS service must be **strategic and agile** to succeed.

The proposed AQUARIUS service may be **implemented and coordinated through an existing entity**, such as Eurofleets, or **partnership of organisations**, bringing together

operators of relevant European research infrastructures. This would enable **efficient realisation of AQUARIUS' Vision**, reducing the administrative burden of establishing a new entity in an already complex organisational landscape.

Opportunities to resource the envisioned service include **existing European frameworks, instruments and co-funding programmes**. This presents an opportunity to **consolidate and optimise funding for transnational access to European marine and freshwater research infrastructures**, including the activity of the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) and Horizon Europe funding programmes that have produced other transnational access projects. Consolidation of RI access funding will make more efficient use of resources, and reduce confusion and application demands among prospective TA users.

The discrete elements of the envisioned service for marine and freshwater RIs enables a **modular approach to resourcing**, allowing separate elements to be funded together or separately, **maximising flexibility, agility and the opportunity to evolve** the service to meet the needs of the research community and European policy priorities.

1. Introduction

AQUARIUS provides access to a comprehensive and diverse suite of integrated research infrastructures to address challenges and explore opportunities for the long-term sustainability of our marine and freshwater ecosystems.

Research infrastructures (RIs) are facilities, resources and services used by the research community to conduct research and promote innovation. They facilitate scientific research within national settings, across borders and in global collaborations. They are of utmost importance for the pursuit of scientific knowledge in a world where research and science are becoming more sophisticated but also more complex; collaboration is key. RIs coordinated via AQUARIUS include research vessels, mobile and fixed observation platforms, aircraft, drones, satellite services, experimental research facilities, river basin supersites and data centres. This integration of such a diversity of *in-* and *ex-situ* marine and freshwater RIs is a first of its kind and serves the need for a more holistic approach to marine and freshwater research and innovation, from source to sea.

Through a robust and transparent system of transnational access funding calls, this four-year Horizon Europe-funded project (March 2024 - February 2028), comprising 45 partners, targets and supports research and innovation activities that contribute to the objectives, regional scope and implementation of the EU Mission 'Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030.' To date, AQUARIUS has granted funding to 11 international projects through its first transnational access call, granting 419 units of access (person days of access), across eighteen research infrastructures. The second AQUARIUS call attracted 42 applications from international research teams seeking to access 65 offered marine and freshwater research infrastructures. Results of the second call are due to be announced in spring 2026.

Funded AQUARIUS projects cover topics as diverse as hydrography and ocean currents impact on climate in the North Atlantic, impacts of ocean processes on biodiversity in the Mediterranean, harmful algal blooms and processes across the land-sea interface in the Black Sea, and volatile organic compound emissions in the Baltic. These projects and applications of AQUARIUS' transnational access offer, and uptake of its other services such as training, demonstrate a high demand for the services provided by the AQUARIUS project, and the wide variety of impactful science that it facilitates.

2. About this document

This document details the AQUARIUS project's vision of excellence in marine and freshwater RIs, proposing a post-project future that will maintain AQUARIUS' legacy and continue to support the Mission 'Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030'. Realisation of AQUARIUS' vision will implement key components of the European Ocean Pact and the Ocean Research & Innovation (R&I) Strategy, facilitate further successes through the All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance, and strengthen the European Research Area. Achieving AQUARIUS' Vision will boost Europe's capacity to advance its leading position in global initiatives, such as the UN Ocean Decade for Sustainable Development.

The AQUARIUS Vision has been developed through a collaborative process engaging all partners in the AQUARIUS project. A questionnaire was circulated to all project partners during 2025, gathering ideas and opinions on the main value of AQUARIUS and the key components that are priorities to sustain after the project ends. Details of this questionnaire and the results are given in Annexe 1. The questionnaire was complemented by targeted interviews with key project partners, giving additional detail and nuance to information, and reviews of related strategic and policy documents. Drafting of this document has been led by Seascope Belgium, in consultation with the AQUARIUS Executive Board and WP7 Partners.

This document forms AQUARIUS deliverable D7.7 and gives an extended version of the "Vision for excellence in marine and freshwater RIs" at the mid-point of the project and in the context of the current evolving landscape of relevant European and international policy and initiatives in early 2026. At the end of the project in early 2028 an updated version of this document will be published as AQUARIUS Milestone 35 and presented in a succinct form at a policy briefing for decision-makers, funders and policymakers during the AQUARIUS final event. The updated version of the Vision will include input collected through consultation with project teams funded through the AQUARIUS transnational access calls.

3. Context

Research infrastructures are indispensable for enabling and developing research and innovation in all scientific domains and often **have broader socio-economic impacts, including increasing Europe's resilience and competitiveness**¹.

Strengthened coordination of, and transnational access to, marine and freshwater research infrastructures are **essential facilitators to achieve the ambitions of a diversity of European policies, initiatives and other priorities** including the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030". Advancing to a mature landscape of integrated European marine and freshwater research infrastructures will be a critical component of the Ocean R&I Strategy, underpinning the Ocean Observation Initiative, as presented in the European Ocean Pact.

With a complexity of marine and freshwater-related challenges facing European society, research infrastructures, and the research they enable, can offer critical support to address a multitude of issues, including through contributions to sustained observing efforts and with dual use applications. These European challenges include protecting and restoring **ocean and freshwater health**, competitiveness of the **EU sustainable blue economy**, support and resilience of **coastal and island communities and outermost regions, water resilience**, the **energy transition**, and the impacts of **climate change** and **biodiversity loss**. Critically the provision of transnational access lowers barriers for access across borders, promoting equity and strengthening the European Research Area.

The **strategic and pragmatic value of sharing RIs** is highlighted by JPI Oceans in their Strategy Framework 2026-2030², noting the potential for enhanced transnational collaboration in marine science, particularly where expensive or specialised equipment and facilities are used. RI sharing, such as that facilitated by AQUARIUS, represents a **high-impact, cost-effective** implementation tool for marine and freshwater science that **maximises the utility of existing national investments**. This is further reflected in the prominence of marine RIs in the strategic plans of the European Ocean Pact.

Investment and strengthened coordination for marine and freshwater research infrastructures will enhance European **autonomy and capacity to address challenges** at national, regional, European and international scales. Advancing collaboration through coordination of European RIs, transnational access and joint research further **enhance science diplomacy and multilateral cooperation** across Europe and beyond,

¹ OECD Report 2025 "Unlocking the potential of research infrastructure ecosystems to tackle societal challenges" https://www.oecd.org/en/publications/unlocking-the-potential-of-research-infrastructure-ecosystems-to-tackle-societal-challenges_4be749f9-en/full-report.html

² JPI Oceans' 2026–2030 Strategy Framework <https://www.jpi-oceans.eu/en/new-strategy-jpi-oceans-bearing-towards-2030>

strengthening the EU's leadership position in international ocean governance, multilateral environmental agreements (MEAs) and other international fora.

With the evolving priorities of some non-EU states, **Europe has a major opportunity and obligation to strengthen its positioning as a global leader in marine and freshwater research, observation and data sharing.** Advanced coordination and sharing between EU Member State's marine and freshwater research infrastructures will be **a key shared European strategic asset** to realise this potential, aligning closely with established and emerging EU marine and freshwater initiatives.

4. AQUARIUS' strategic vision for the European Marine and Freshwater Research Infrastructures of the future

The AQUARIUS' strategic vision is for **a sustained European service to support marine and freshwater research infrastructures,** and the excellent science they facilitate, in support of the EU Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030" and implementation of the European Ocean Pact.

The sustained AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater research infrastructures includes:

- A resourced programme for **transnational access** to European marine and freshwater research infrastructures for research teams worldwide
- Technical **training** opportunities and resources for early career researchers and technicians, e.g. by maintenance of the AQUARIUS Technical Training Hub and Materials Repository
- **Data management** and Open Science support, e.g. by maintenance of the AQUARIUS Data Flow Dashboard and data pathways to EMODnet and the European Digital Twin Ocean.
- A living **inventory of European marine and freshwater research infrastructures,** including their technical and scientific capabilities and facilities, e.g. by maintenance, expansion and further development of the AQUARIUS catalogue
- Facilitation of a **forum for marine and freshwater RI operators and technicians** to share expertise, best practices and support.

Realisation of AQUARIUS' strategic vision for European Marine and Freshwater Research Infrastructures will be **critical to continue to support excellent, internationally collaborative aquatic science,** as demonstrated during the AQUARIUS project.

5. AQUARIUS and priority initiatives for Europe

Beyond supporting excellent science and research, the envisioned AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater research infrastructures will support implementation of a range of ambitious policies, initiatives and strategic activities for Europe.

5.1. Mission "Restore our Oceans and Waters by 2030"

Research infrastructures are central to achieving the objectives of the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters by 2030." They provide the advanced observation, monitoring, and research capacity required to generate the high-quality, interoperable data needed to understand, protect, and restore Europe's aquatic environments and ecosystems. By enabling research that tracks pollution, assesses biodiversity and

ecosystem health, and measures the effects of climate change and human activity, RIs supply the scientific foundation for developing and deploying innovative solutions from source to sea.

A sustained AQUARIUS service would play a critical role in coordinating and supporting these infrastructures to maximise their contribution to the Mission.

By providing a central and unique platform for collaboration, transnational access, and data exchange in marine and freshwater research and innovation, a sustained AQUARIUS service would ensure that researchers from public, private and civil society sectors across Europe can effectively collaborate, share methodologies, and apply best practices. The delivery of FAIR data by AQUARIUS funded projects to key European systems such as EMODnet, Copernicus, and the European Digital Twin Ocean would ensure that the knowledge generated through RIs informs policy, and drives innovation and restoration initiatives, accelerating progress towards healthy, resilient oceans and waters and a sustainable, climate neutral blue economy.

As the Mission enters its second 'deployment and upscaling' phase (2026-2030), a sustained AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater RIs will be an **essential facilitator** to achieve its objectives and meet its targets, including through provision of critical data to the **European Digital Twin Ocean**. Beyond 2030, a sustained AQUARIUS service will serve to continue the Mission's legacy and strengthen Europe's capacity to address emerging challenges for our oceans and waters.

5.2. European Ocean Pact and the Ocean R&I Strategy

The European Ocean Pact depends on robust, holistic and coordinated science to guide its implementation. Coordinated RIs are key to generating the essential knowledge to restore and protect marine environments through continuous observation, sampling and experimentation, enabling understanding of ocean dynamics, ecosystem health and human impacts.

A sustained AQUARIUS service would **support transformation of Europe's fragmented research infrastructure landscape into a unified and cooperative engine for effective and sustainable ocean knowledge and management** - a key aim of the Ocean Pact. This sustained service would enable scientists across Europe and worldwide to share research infrastructure, data and expertise. Through its open calls and collaborative framework, a sustained AQUARIUS service will help level the playing field for researchers by granting access to state-of-the-art infrastructures based on scientific excellence rather than institutional or national resources. By funding access to costly and technically demanding facilities, a sustained AQUARIUS service will empower talented scientists to carry out research that may otherwise be beyond reach. This approach promotes equity, diversity and inclusion within the marine and freshwater research community, **ensuring that Europe's collective science and innovation potential is fully mobilised to achieve the ambitions of the Ocean Pact**, and that knowledge generation is driven by excellence, not individual access to resources.

5.3. EU and international environmental policy

By maintaining a long-term, integrated platform that connects European research infrastructures, **a sustained AQUARIUS service will make marine, freshwater and environmental monitoring programmes more efficient, cost-effective and scientifically robust**, supporting implementation of the Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD), the Water Framework Directive (WFD), Maritime Spatial Planning Directive (MSPD), the Regional Sea Conventions, the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdictions (BBNJ) Agreement and a number of other EU, regional and international environmental policy and legislation. It will support the development and validation of

innovative observation technologies, from sensors to autonomous systems, improving how Europe measures and understands water quality, ecosystem health and pollution pathways, and identifies emerging threats to marine and freshwater environments. Shared infrastructure access and services will also enhance early warning and forecasting capabilities, enabling faster responses to environmental degradation and **supporting Member States to meet their obligations.**

Beyond its technical role, a sustained AQUARIUS service will provide a collaborative hub that **builds capacity across EU Member States and reduces disparities in monitoring and research capabilities.** By pooling resources and expertise, countries with limited access to advanced infrastructures will be supported to meet EU monitoring obligations and contribute to shared datasets according to agreed standards. In doing so, a sustained AQUARIUS service would **promote coherence and comparability between river catchments and sea basins, and interoperability between reported monitoring data, creating a stronger scientific foundation for coordinated water management and policy evaluation.** Ultimately, a sustained AQUARIUS service for RIs has the potential to help transform fragmented national efforts into a connected European system capable of delivering the continuous knowledge flow needed to safeguard Europe's waters.

5.4. All-Atlantic Ocean Research and Innovation Alliance (AAORIA)

Research infrastructures provide the shared physical and technological foundation that enables researchers from across the Atlantic to observe, sample and model the ocean as a single, interconnected system. By harmonising methodologies, standards and observing technologies across continents, **coordinated RIs help generate coherent and comparable data, making understanding of large-scale phenomena possible,** such as ocean circulation, biodiversity shifts and carbon cycling that transcend national boundaries.

The collaborative use of marine and freshwater RIs fosters scientific diplomacy, building trust and long-term cooperation between research communities across Europe, Africa, the Americas and the Caribbean. A sustained AQUARIUS service, including its transnational access and training components, will **strengthen collective capacity across the Atlantic** to address shared challenges in climate, ecosystems and sustainable resource use.

A sustained AQUARIUS service would take this collaboration further, acting as a bridge between European infrastructures and transatlantic partners, streamlining access and promoting reciprocity in ocean research. By coordinating opportunities for shared use of European facilities and data systems, **AQUARIUS can support partner countries to integrate their observation assets and research capabilities into a wider Atlantic network.**

5.5. European Research Area

Research infrastructures are the backbone of the European Research Area. They promote and enable transnational collaboration, training and exchange of data, information, expertise and best practices. **Transnational access programmes facilitate equity of access to these resources, allowing researchers to work collaboratively across borders.** Coordinated RIs can help to align national research strategies and allow the EU to **mobilise collective capacity on major scientific and societal challenges,** from climate adaptation to the sustainable use of marine and freshwater ecosystems.

A sustained AQUARIUS service would **directly support the goals of the European Research Area** by coordinating access to marine and freshwater research infrastructures across Europe, removing bottlenecks to researcher collaboration and mobility. By harmonising application processes and ensuring transparent, merit-based access, AQUARIUS reduces the barriers that currently restrain transnational research. Its role in linking observational platforms, training programmes and data practices strengthens knowledge exchange and open, interoperable monitoring networks that underpin evidence-based policy and innovation. In doing so, **AQUARIUS helps create a more inclusive, attractive and globally competitive European environment for research and scientific careers.**

5.6. UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development

The UN Decade of Ocean Science for Sustainable Development calls for stronger, more connected ocean research to tackle key global challenges and support the implementation of the wider Agenda 2030. **Marine and freshwater research infrastructures are central to this effort** as they provide the long-term observations, experimental facilities and data systems needed to understand ecosystem change, monitor pollution, track climate impacts and evaluate restoration and management strategies.

A sustained AQUARIUS service supporting and coordinating European marine and freshwater RIs will be a valuable asset to tackle all ten UN Ocean Decade challenges.

6. Structure, governance and resourcing

The record of the AQUARIUS project clearly demonstrates the demand for the services it offers, and the impactful research it facilitates. It also demonstrates the effectiveness of such a model for coordination of RIs. **Simply, AQUARIUS works.** Appropriate, sustained implementation of the proposed AQUARIUS service for marine and freshwater research infrastructures will be key to successful realisation of its potential. With limited resources and a complex existing landscape of European marine and freshwater entities, programmes and RIs, implementation of a sustained AQUARIUS service must be **strategic and agile** to succeed.

The proposed AQUARIUS service may be **implemented and coordinated through an existing entity**, such as Eurofleets, or **partnership of organisations**, bringing together operators of relevant European research infrastructures. This would enable **efficient realisation of AQUARIUS' Vision**, reducing the administrative burden of establishing a new entity in an already complex organisational landscape.

Opportunities to resource the envisioned service include **existing European frameworks, instruments and co-funding programmes**. This presents an opportunity to **consolidate and optimise funding for transnational access to European marine and freshwater research infrastructures**, including the activity of the Sustainable Blue Economy Partnership (SBEP) and Horizon Europe funding programmes that have produced transnational access projects including AQUARIUS, Eurofleets, POLARIN and ARICE. Consolidation of RI access funding will make more efficient use of resources, and reduce confusion and application demands among prospective TA users.

The discrete elements of the envisioned service for marine and freshwater RIs, enables a **modular approach to resourcing**, allowing separate elements to be funded together or separately, **maximising flexibility, agility and the opportunity to evolve** the service to meet the needs of the research community and European policy priorities.

Annexe 1: AQUARIUS legacy vision and policy brief - partners questionnaire

Below are the questions included in the questionnaire for AQUARIUS partners used as the initial tool to gather input to this document. In total 24 questionnaire responses were recorded.

The questionnaire was complemented by targeted interviews with AQUARIUS consortium members and reviews of related strategic and policy documents.

Section 1 – About you and your role in AQUARIUS

1. Full name
2. Email address
3. Partner organisation
4. Are you an AQUARIUS RI provider/operator? (Yes/No)
5. If yes, what type of RI do you provide or operate? (Select all that apply)
 - a. Research vessels
 - b. Mobile marine observation platforms
 - c. Fixed marine facilities
 - d. Experimental research facility
 - e. River and basin supersites
 - f. Aircraft
 - g. Drones
 - h. Satellite services
 - i. Data centres and virtual labs
 - j. I am not an AQUARIUS RI provider or operator
 - k. Other (define)
6. Which AQUARIUS work packages do you contribute to? (Select all that apply)
 - a. WP1 - Coordination and Project Management
 - b. WP2 - Transnational Access
 - c. WP3 - Research Infrastructure Call Design, Management, Evaluation and Access Platform
 - d. WP4 - Research Infrastructure Access Facilitation & Management and Governance
 - e. WP5 - Research Infrastructure Technical Training
 - f. WP6 - Data Management and Open Science Practices
 - g. WP7 - Impact: Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication

Section 2 – Your vision for sustaining AQUARIUS' legacy

7. What do you understand by the term "research infrastructure"?
8. What do you see as the most valuable benefits that AQUARIUS provides? (choose up to 3)
 - a. Funded access to research infrastructure for international teams
 - b. Collaboration and exchange of ideas and knowledge with similar organisations and other RI operators
 - c. Training to early career researchers
 - d. FAIR data provision
 - e. Support for excellent science to advance marine and freshwater knowledge
 - f. Networking of the marine and freshwater science communities
 - g. Policy advice supporting the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters"
 - h. Other (define)

9. Which aspects of AQUARIUS would you most like to see be sustained after the project ends? (choose up to 3)
 - a. Funded access to research infrastructure for international teams
 - b. Collaboration and exchange of ideas and knowledge with similar organisations and other RI operators
 - c. Training to early career researchers
 - d. FAIR data provision
 - e. Support for excellent science to advance marine and freshwater knowledge
 - f. Networking of the marine and freshwater science communities
 - g. Policy advice supporting the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters"
 - h. Other (define)
10. Which aspects of AQUARIUS would you **not** like to see maintained after the project ends?
 - a. Funded access to research infrastructure for international teams
 - b. Collaboration and exchange of ideas and knowledge with similar organisations and other RI operators
 - c. Training to early career researchers
 - d. FAIR data provision
 - e. Support for excellent science to advance marine and freshwater knowledge
 - f. Networking of the marine and freshwater science communities
 - g. Policy advice supporting the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters"
 - h. Other (define)
11. What do you see as the greatest challenge in continuing to provide AQUARIUS' benefits after the project ends?
 - a. Funding and resources
 - b. Organisational structure and governance
 - c. Change in policy priorities
 - d. Maintaining the network and community of organisations involved in AQUARIUS
 - e. Maintaining a network of marine and freshwater communities together
 - f. Other (define)
12. Considering your previous answers, what kind of structure or entity would be most suitable to maintain AQUARIUS' legacy after the project ends?
 - a. Long-term funded programme
 - b. (Funded) network of RIs
 - c. AQUARIUS legal entity/organisation/association
 - d. AQUARIUS ESFRI Landmark
 - e. AQUARIUS ERIC
 - f. Maintain AQUARIUS' legacy via the Eurofleets AISBL
 - g. Further project-based initiatives
 - h. Other (define)
13. Considering your previous answers, what kind of structure or entity would **not** be suitable to maintain AQUARIUS' legacy after the project ends? (Multiple possible)
 - a. Long-term funded programme
 - b. (Funded) network of RIs
 - c. AQUARIUS legal entity/organisation/association
 - d. AQUARIUS ESFRI Landmark
 - e. AQUARIUS ERIC
 - f. Maintain AQUARIUS' legacy via the Eurofleets AISBL
 - g. Further project-based initiatives
 - h. Other (define)
14. Are there successful examples of similar projects sustaining their legacy, which AQUARIUS could emulate? Eurofleets and EUFAR have been highlighted as

- examples. Any others would be welcome. Please provide a short comment on why/what aspects of these examples could be useful to AQUARIUS.
15. Who do you think are the most influential actors in helping to sustain AQUARIUS legacy?
 - a. RI operators
 - b. Scientists
 - c. Funders
 - d. Policymakers
 - e. Other (define)
 16. AQUARIUS is a contributing project to the EU Mission "Restore our Ocean and Waters". Do you see this as an important initiative for AQUARIUS to continue to align with?
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Maybe
 - d. Don't know
 17. Please provide give short explanation to your answer to question 16.
 18. What could the European Commission do to support the legacy of AQUARIUS?
 19. What could other policymakers/funders (national/regional) do to support the legacy of AQUARIUS?
 20. What can RI providers/operators do to support the AQUARIUS legacy?

Section 3 – Anything else?

21. Please add any other comments or suggestions you may have.

End of questionnaire.